

NANOFACTS

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1. INTRODUCTION

As part of the Plan for the Exploitation and Dissemination of Results (PEDR) in NANOFACETS, the present Deliverable details the participation and/or presentation of NANOFACETS researchers at conferences and other events from March 2022 to June 2024.

Attendance and participation to scientific conferences and other type of events was included as part of the planned activities in order to gain and keep up-to-date knowledge with the latest developments in research related to cancer theranostics and cancer-related biosensors and to provide opportunities for enhancing/establishing potential collaborations.

2. REPORT ON PARTICIPATION OF BIOS-RESEARCHERS AT CONFERENCES

2.1 23rd IEEE International Conference on Nanotechnology, IEEE Nano 2023

Staff involved: MSc Ivana Kundačina, MSc Aleksandra Pavlović, Dr. Nikola Knežević

Place: Palma de Mallorca, Spain

Date: 04 – 08 July 2022

Website: <https://2022.ieeenano.org/>

Goal: Presenting NANOFACETS research and networking in nanomaterial and nanosensors community

In Palma de Mallorca, Dr. Nikola Knežević delivered a presentation during the conference, contributing to the session focusing on nano-biomedicine. He was accompanied by Ivana Kundačina (ex Podunavac) and Aleksandra Pavlović, who actively participated in the event. Their presence facilitated extensive networking opportunities and provided comprehensive insights into diverse research endeavours within the realms of nanobiomedicine, nanosensors, and nanofabrication.

Figure 1. NANOFACETS team at the IEEE Nano23 Conference.

2.2 HYMA2022 (7th International Conference on Multifunctional, Hybrid and Nanomaterials)

Staff involved: Dr. Amelia Ultimo

Place: Genoa, Italy

Date: 19–22 October 2022

Website: <https://www.innomem.eu/event/7th-international-conference-on-multifunctional-hybrid-and-nanomaterials/>

Goal: Presenting research and establishing collaborations

Dr Amelia Ultimo attended HYMA2022 (7th International Conference on Multifunctional, Hybrid and Nanomaterials) In Genoa, Italy. This is a large, international, and interdisciplinary conference focused on hybrid materials where around 1000 researchers from all over the world shared their research through oral sessions and poster's presentations. Dr Ultimo presented the results obtained by the team on the development of a combination strategy (targeted cancer-derived exosomes and stimuli-responsive mesoporous silica nanoparticles) for the treatment of neuroblastoma and glioblastoma multiforme using 2D and 3D cultures.

Figure 2. Dr. Amelia Ultimo at the 7th International Conference on Multifunctional, Hybrid and Nanomaterials in Italy.

15th International Scientific Conference "Students Encountering Science"

Staff involved: MSc Mila Đisalov, MSc Aleksandra Pavlović

Place: Banja Luka, Bosnia and Herzegovina

Date: 17 - 19 November 2022

Website: <https://stes.unibl.org/>

Goal: Presenting research and regional networking

Brief report:

MSc Mila Đisalov and MSc Aleksandra Pavlović, actively participated in the 15th International Scientific Conference "Students Encountering Science" held in Banja Luka, Bosnia and Herzegovina. The primary objective of the conference, known as StES, is to stimulate and cultivate the research endeavors of young scholars while fostering a culture of academic excellence. Through its platform, StES aims to promote the cultivation of scholarly inquiry among the youth. During the event, Mila Đisalov delivered an oral presentation elucidating her abstract titled "LAMP Primer Design for Monitoring Gene Expression of Tumor Markers in 3D Cancer Cultures." Likewise, Aleksandra Pavlović shared her research through an oral presentation titled "Nanosensor for Glutathione".

Figure 3. MSc Mila Đisalov and MSc Aleksandra Pavlović at 15th International Scientific Conference "Students Encountering Science"

2.3 International Meet on Pharmaceutics and Drug Delivery Systems (Pharmameet2023)

Staff involved: Dr. Nikola Knežević

Place: Porto, Portugal

Date: 09 – 11 February 2023

Website: <https://10times.com/e12r-khzp-6p16>

Goal: Delivering keynote lecture and presenting latest NANOFACETS research

Dr. Nikola Knežević attended the International Meet on Pharmaceutics and Drug Delivery Systems (Pharmameet2023), hosted in Porto, Portugal. As a distinguished participant, Dr. Knežević assumed the role of keynote speaker, delivering a presentation on "Cyclodextrin-Capped Mesoporous Silica-Based Nanomaterials for pH-Responsive Targeted Theranostics of Glioblastoma Multiforme". This lecture served to elucidate the significant advancements and applications of nanotechnology in the realm of pharmaceuticals, particularly in the context of developing innovative and responsive therapies tailored for Glioblastoma Multiforme.

Figure 4 Dr. Nikola Knežević at Pharmameet 2023 in Porto, Portugal.

2.4 20th International Conference on Nanosciences & Nanotechnologies

Staff involved: Dr. Nikola Knežević

Place: Thessaloniki, Greece

Date: 04 – 07 July 2023

Website: <https://rc.auth.gr/en/conference/151>

Goal: Presenting NANOFACETS research

Dr. Nikola Knežević was an active participant in the 20th International Conference on Nanosciences & Nanotechnologies, convened in Thessaloniki, Greece. Throughout the conference, Dr. Knežević delivered a comprehensive presentation, providing notable insights into the progress and advancements of the NANOFACETS project. Specifically, emphasis was placed on the ongoing development endeavors about theranostic nanoparticles designed for both the treatment and magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) diagnostics of Glioblastoma Multiforme.

Figure 5. Dr. Nikola Knežević presenting results in Thessaloniki, Greece.

2.5 35th International Conference “Eurosensors 2023

Staff involved: Stefan Jarić

Place: Lecce, Italy

Date: 10 - 13 September 2023

Website: <https://www.eurosensors2023.eu/>

Goal: Presentation of NANOFACETS research conducted during ESR visit to TUW

Stefan Jarić attended the 35th International Conference “Eurosensors 2023” held in Lecce, Italy, where he presented his latest research obtained during his visit to Vienna University of Technology (TUW) at Prof. Peter Ertl’s lab. The title of his oral presentation was “Electrochemical Detection of MMP-2 Using Graphene-Based Aptasensor”, which he presented during the session Biomedical sensors & diagnostics I. Also, the abstract is published in MDPI Proceedings (<https://doi.org/10.3390/proceedings2024097057>). Stefan's talk was dedicated to low-cost and simple technology for biosensor development, where the fully electrochemical approach was used to fabricate a reduced graphene oxide aptasensor and detect MMP2 in a PBS medium.

Figure 6. MSc Stefan Jarić presenting research at Eurosensors 2023 in Lecce, Italy.

2.6 CoMBoS conference

Staff involved: MSc Mila Đisalov, MSc Teodora Knežić, MSc Marija Pavlović

Place: Belgrade, Serbia

Date: 6-8 October 2023.

Website: https://d1fdloi71mui9q.cloudfront.net/Vkir6LD8S4WcPnJDxiNF_CoMBoS-Drugo_obave%C5%A1tenje.pdf

Goal: Regional networking and gaining knowledge in the field of Molecular Biology

During the CoMBoS conference our ESRs Mila Đisalov and Teodora Knežić attended training session titled "iPSCs Spring School: iPSCs as a tool for modeling disease and discovering molecular mechanisms of NDDs" where they got to chance to learn about the use of iPSCs as cell models for cancer monitoring which is of great importance for our NANOFACETS research.

Understanding the potential of induced pluripotent stem cells (iPSCs) in studying various diseases, including neurodegenerative disorders and cancer, is pivotal for advancements in medical research. These tiny powerhouses allow us to explore disease mechanisms and develop new therapies.

Figure 7. MSc Mila Djisalov, MSc Teodora Knežić and MSc Marija Pavlović at CoMBoS Conference in Belgrade, Serbia.

2.7 Chemical Engineering Days 2024. The Chemical Engineering Conference 2024

Staff involved: MSc Ivana Milosević

Place: Veszprem, Hungary

Date: 16-17 April, 2024.

Website: <https://mkn.uni-pannon.hu/index.php/en/program.html>

Goal: Presenting NANOFACETS research related to biosensors development

MSc Ivana Milosevic, Junior Researcher from BioSense Institute, participated in the Műszaki Kémiai Napok (MKN) 2024, an international conference held from April 16 to April 17, 2024, in Veszprém, Hungary. During this conference, Ivana delivered an oral presentation titled "Advancements in Low-Cost Biosensor Manufacturing: A Novel Approach for Rapid Electrochemical Biosensor Production." I. Milosevic *, I. Kundacina, N. Knezevic and V. Radonic. The presentation emphasized the significance of biosensors as powerful analytical tools aiding in understanding biological processes. Their applications as alternatives to standard microbiology tests across various fields, including biomedicine, environmental monitoring, and food safety, were highlighted. Biosensors' design to detect and quantify specific biological molecules by converting interactions into measurable signals was explained. The fundamental components of biosensors were also discussed, focusing on the biorecognition element (biomolecule) and the transducer that converts the biological response into a quantifiable signal. Recent research highlighting gold as an ideal substrate for electrochemical biosensors due to its chemical stability and affinity for binding biomolecules modified with thiol groups was presented. Various immobilization strategies for diverse biorecognition elements, including aptamers, antibodies, and flagella, were showcased for single and multiplex detection of pathogens (E. coli and Salmonella), cortisol as an animal stress hormone, and tumor biomarkers like MMP2 and HER2, demonstrating applications in healthcare, environmental monitoring, and food safety.

Figure 8. MSc Ivana Milosević at Chemical Engineer Day 2024 conference in Veszprem, Hungary.

2.8 9th International congress of biomaterials and biosensors BIOMATSEN 2024

Staff involved: Dr Vasa Radonić

Place: Olydeniz, Turkey

Date: 18-24 April 2024.

Website: <https://www.biomatsencongress.org/>

Goal: Invited talk - Presenting NANOFACTS research related to biosensors development

Dr. Vasa Radonic took stage as a keynote speaker at the 9th International congress of biomaterials and biosensors BIOMATSEN 2024 held from April 18 to 24, 2024, in Olydeniz, Turkey presenting a talk entitled “Innovations in Gold Electrode Manufacturing for Cost-effective Biosensors”. During the gathering, Dr. Radonić shared research results in the field of biosensors development and proposed a newly developed technology for the realization of low-cost biosensor platform with a potential in detecting different tumor biomarkers. By speaking at this event, Dr. Radonić not only shed light on cutting-edge research but also encouraged collaboration among fellow researchers and students. This sharing of knowledge promises to advance our understanding of how biosensors can help in the fight against cancer.

Figure 9. Dr Vasa Radonić at BIOMATSEN 2024 conference in Oludeniz, Turkey.

2.9 8th International Conference on Bio-Sensing Technology

Staff involved: Dr. Nikola Knežević, MSc Stefan Jarić, MSc Ivana Milosević

Place: Seville, Spain

Date: 12-15 May 2024

Website: <https://www.elsevier.com/events/conferences/all/international-conference-on-bio-sensing-technology>

Goal: Attending the 8th International Conference on Bio-Sensing Technology and poster presentation of the research partly supported by NANOFACTS

Dr. Nikola Knežević, MSc Ivana Milosević and MSc Stefan Jarić attended the 8th International Conference on Bio-Sensing Technology, organized by Elsevier and held in Seville, Spain, from May 12-15. Dr. Knežević gave a talk entitled: "Novel Cost-effective Electrochemical Systems for Sensing Cancer Biomarkers.". This work, in its final stages, explores promising avenues for enhancing cancer detection through affordable electrochemical methods. Stefan presented his latest research obtained with the support of the NANOFACTS project through a poster presentation. The title of his presentation was "Low-cost approach for determination of NTproBNP in saliva using graphene-based aptasensor", which he presented during the poster session 2. Stefan's poster elaborated on a low-cost and simple technology for biosensor development based on reduced graphene oxide FETs, which was assembled in an aptasensor for the ultrasensitive determination of NTproBNP in artificial saliva as a real-sample model. The presentation was focused on the two-parameter analysis of the sensor signal development, explaining the physics behind the aptasensor working principle. MSc Ivana Milosevic presented paper entitled "Gold leaf electrochemical biosensor utilizing flagellar filament for sensitive Ni detection" in the poster session, related to the development of biosensors based on flagellar filaments.

Figure 10. Dr. Nikola Knežević presenting at the 8th International Conference on Bio-Sensing Technology in Seville, Spain.

Figure 11. MSc Stefan Jarić at 8th International Conference on Bio-Sensing Technology in Seville, Spain.

2.10 The 4th International Electronic Conference on Biosensors, IECB 2024

Staff involved: Dr. Slavica Savić Ružić, MSc Stefan Jarić

Place: online

Date: 20 – 22 May 2024

Website: <https://sciforum.net/event/IECB2024?section=#program>

The 4th International Electronic Conference on Biosensors (IECB 2024) was held online from May 20-22, 2024. The conference successfully gathered global experts to share and exchange knowledge on the latest advancements and applications of biosensors. Presentations covered diverse topics such as environmental monitoring, disease detection, food safety, defense, and drug discovery. The event also focused on engaging young scientists, encouraging their active participation and contributions to the field.

Figure 12. Certificates of Participation for Dr. Slavica Savić Ružić and MSc Stefan Jarić at IECB 2024.

2.11 NANOSPAIN 2024

Staff involved: Dr. Nikola Knežević

Place: Tarragona, Spain

Date: 04 – 07 June 2024

Website: <https://www.nanospainconf.org/2024/index.php>

Goal: Presenting NANOFACETS research and networking

Dr. Knežević recently presented final research from the NANOFACETS project at the NANOSPAIN 2024 conference held in Tarragona, Spain from June 4th to June 7th. His presentation delved into "Potential of MRI-based Sensing of Cargo Release from Mesoporous Silica for Tracking Drug Delivery Capabilities" presenting research published in the final stages of project. The conference brought together leading experts and researchers in the field of nanotechnology to explore the latest advancements and discoveries. It served as a platform for networking, collaboration, and fostering innovative solutions to pressing global challenges across various research areas.

Figure 13. Dr. Nikola Knežević at NANOSPAIN 2024 Conference in Tarragona, Spain

2.12 9th European Congress on Advanced Nanotechnology and Nanomaterials

Staff involved: Dr Vasa Radonić

Place: Amsterdam, Netherlands

Date: 24-25 June 2024.

Website: <https://nanomaterialsconference.com/>

Goal: Participation at conference and workshop related to microfluidics development

Dr. Vasa Radonic took stage as a keynote speaker at the 9th International congress of biomaterials and biosensors BIOMATSEN 2024 held from April 18 to 24, 2024, in Olydeniz, Turkey presenting a talk entitled “Innovations in Gold Electrode Manufacturing for Cost-effective Biosensors”. During the gathering, Dr. Radonić shared research results in the field of biosensors development and propose a newly developed technology for the realization of low-cost biosensor platform with a potential in detecting different tumor biomarkers. By speaking at this event, Dr. Knežević not only shed light on cutting-edge research but also encouraged collaboration among fellow researchers and students. This sharing of knowledge promises to advance our understanding of how biosensors can help in the fight against cancer.

Figure 14. *Dr Vasa Radonić at 9th European Congress on Advanced Nanotechnology and Nanomaterials conference*

3. REPORT ON PARTICIPATION OF BIOS-RESEARCHERS AT OTHER EVENTS

3.1. NANOFACTS Training School

Staff involved: BIOS researchers

Place: BioSense Institute Rectorate Building & Science & Technology Park, Novi Sad

Date: 27th June – 1st July 2022

Website: <https://www.nanofacts.net/training-school/>

Goal: Learn state-of-the-art research achievements in cancer diagnosis, therapy and imaging, familiarizing with soft skills and problem solving skills, and hands-on workshops

A total of 79 interested participants registered for the event via the **NANOFACTS** webpage, comprising students, researchers, professors from outside the **NANOFACTS** consortium, and invited lecturers.

In total, 52 participants attended the lectures on the first day of the **NANOFACTS** Training School related to cancer biosensing. The structure of participants was as follows: 23 students, 8 BIOS students, 26 researchers, 3 experts from partner institutions, 6 external experts, and 15 BIOS researchers.

During the second day, a total of 49 people attended the lectures. Of this number, 13 attendees were employed at BIOS, 25 were young scientists (junior researchers and students), and 24 were experienced researchers.

The third day was dedicated to learning about soft skills and problem-solving, with 46 participants, of which 13 were students and 33 were researchers (junior and senior).

Figure 15. Lecture Presentations

Figure 16. Hands-on training session conducted by Eliana Manobianco and Francesco Floris on biochemical analyzer using imaging surface plasmon resonance, alongside a workshop led by Dr. Amelia Ultimo on in vitro assessment of therapeutic nanomaterials in both 2D and 3D cell cultures

Figure 17. Workshop lecture delivered by dr. Oliviero Gobbo on the topic of "Designing Animal Experiments"

In total, 33 attendees participated in a training session focusing on cancer biosensing, comprising 27 BIOS staff, 13 BIOS students, 14 BIOS senior researchers, 1 BIOS technician, and 2 TCD researchers. On the fifth day of the TS week, three workshop lectures (WSLs) focusing on Cancer Theranostic Nanomaterials were conducted. A total of 30 individuals attended these lectures. Among them, 23 were BIOS employees, 12 were young scientists (including junior researchers and students), and 18 were experienced researchers.

3.2 Science to Business Camp

Staff involved: MSc Mirjana Mundžić

Place: Congress Centre of SAS Smolenice, Slovakia

Date: 17 – 20 August 2022

Website: <https://inova.to/en/event/science-to-business-camp/>

Goal: Learn how to get science closer to business, how to commercialize research, bring it to public use and make profit.

Mirjana Mundžić, participated in “Science to Business Camp” in Smolenice Castle, Slovakia, organized by [INOVATO](#) Cluster. She attended and actively participated in more than 15 lectures and workshops organized on the topic of commercialization of scientific research. These events were prepared by 10 speakers who covered a wide range of topics, including preparing presentation of ideas and financial plans, intellectual property protection, selecting funding sources, and other relevant aspects. The most valuable insights were shared by Stephen Russo, author of the book "Science Commercialization," and Pavol Čekan, CEO of the innovative biotechnology company MultiplexDX, specializing in molecular biology, biochemistry, and oncology. Their success stories provided inspiration and practical insights into the process of commercializing scientific research.

Through these events, Mirjana gained knowledge and contacts that will be invaluable for her future projects and collaboration between science and industry. These experiences will enable her to more effectively develop and implement new ideas, as well as establish sustainable connections between the academic community and industry.

Figure 18. MSc Mirjana Mundžić at Science to Business Camp in Smolenice Castle, Slovakia.

3.3 Open Science Communication 2022

Staff involved: MSc Stefan Jarić and MSc Aleksandra Pavlović

Place: Belgrade, Serbia

Date: 24 – 25 November 2022

Website: <https://stillinbelgrade.com/open-science-communication-conference-opensicomm-2022/>

Goal: Learning about the concept of Science Communication - public presenting science- related topics

Brief report: Open Science Communication 2022 was International Conference organized by Center for the Promotion of Science with an aim of strengthening the understanding of science and increasing scientific literacy as an indispensable part of everyday life. One of the main goals of this conference was to promote the concept of Science Communication as it refers to public presenting science-related topics not only among scientists but primarily targeting all social strata. Participation in the conference broadened the horizons and stimulated the critical thinking of researchers, and it also encouraged the development of new ideas in the presentation of scientific research data and results.

Figure 19. MSc Aleksandra Pavlović and MSc Stefan Jarić at Open Science Communication Conference in Belgrade, Serbia

3.4 NETPORE 2nd International Training School

Staff involved: Dr. Nikola Knežević

Place: Athens, Greece

Date: 17 - 20 July 2023

Website: <https://netpore.eu/TSAth/speakers.php?evt=14>

Goal: presenting NANOFACTS research

Dr. Nikola Knežević took stage as a keynote speaker at the NETPORE 2nd International Training School held from July 17 to 20, 2023, in Athens, Greece. This special event was hosted by the Institute of Nanoscience and Nanotechnology at the National Centre for Scientific Research "Demokritos." During the gathering, Dr. Knežević shared insights into the use of tiny particles mesoporous silica and organosilica nanoparticles and their exciting potential in detecting glioblastoma cancer, treating it, and imaging. By speaking at this event, Dr. Knežević shed light on cutting-edge research and encouraged collaboration among fellow researchers and students. This sharing of knowledge promises to advance our understanding of how nanotechnology can help in the fight against cancer.

2nd International Training school, July 17-20, 2023 (Athens, Greece)

Mesoporous silica nanoparticles: functionalization, characterization and applications for cancer sensing, therapy and imaging

Dr. Nikola Knežević

Figure 20. Dr. Nikola Knežević, a keynote speaker at the NETPORE Conference in Athens, Greece.

3.5 A three-day virtual Workshop held by Ratul Kumar Das, Ph.D.

Staff involved: Mirjana Mundžić

Place: online

Date: 09 – 11 August 2023

Website: <https://nanoschool.in/>

Goal: Workshop “Designing Nanoparticles for Targeted Cancer Therapy”

Brief report:

Mirjana Mundžić actively participated in a three-day virtual Workshop held by Ratul Kumar Das, Ph.D., specialized scientist in Nanobiotechnology, research consultant from Save The Environment, India.

The workshop covered a range of essential topics aimed at advancing the understanding of nanoparticle applications in cancer treatment. Sessions included an in-depth exploration of the fundamentals of nanoparticles, their unique properties, and their potential for targeted cancer therapy. Attendees delved into cancer biology basics to gain insights into the biology of cancer cells and its significance in crafting precise therapeutic strategies. Also, different methodologies for tailoring nanoparticles to specific cancer types and tumor microenvironments were discussed. Participants were engaged in insightful discussions on targeting mechanisms, exploring ligands and surface modifications that facilitate enhanced precision in targeting cancer cells. Nanoparticle imaging and tracking techniques were explored for their ability to visualize and monitor nanoparticles *in vivo* during cancer treatment. Moreover, the Workshop addressed the critical

subject of nanotoxicology and safety considerations, ensuring a comprehensive understanding of the safety and potential toxicity concerns associated with nanoparticle-based therapies.

Figure 21. MSc Mirjana Mundžić at a three-day virtual Workshop

3.6 NETPORE Webinar

Staff involved: Mirjana Mundžić

Place: online

Date: 21 September 2023

Website: <https://netpore.eu/WebinarSeptember21/index.php?evt=18>

Goal: Presenting NANOFACTS research

Mirjana Mundžić held a presentation titled “Mesoporous silica nanoparticles (MSNs) for glioblastoma multiforme theranostics”. The presentation provided an overview of mesoporous silica nanoparticles (MSNs), including their synthesis, functionalization, and characterization. Recent findings regarding the loading of MSN pores with dyes, drugs, and contrast agents were discussed, all aimed at achieving controlled drug delivery to specific targets, particularly within glioblastoma multiforme cells. Additionally, the potential utility of MSN for cancer diagnostics using MRI imaging was shown.

Figure 22. MSc Mirjana Mundžić presenting “Mesoporous silica nanoparticles (MSNs) for glioblastoma multiforme theranostics” at NETPORE Webinar.

3.7 Course: How to Communicate Modern Science?

Staff involved: MSc Minja Mladenović

Place: Belgrade, Serbia

Date: 12 – 14 December 2023

Website: <https://www.cpn.edu.rs/kurs-kako-komunicirati-savremenu-nauku/?script=cir>

Goal: Spreading knowledge about effective science communication in today's dynamic landscape

Brief report:

Our researcher, Minja Mladenović, attended first science communication conference, the groundbreaking "How to Communicate Modern Science?" course in Serbia. This innovative three-day interdisciplinary event, the first of its kind in Serbia, connected doctoral and master's students alongside young researchers across all scientific fields. Led by Dr. Darko Donevski, an astrophysicist and science communicator, the course explored essential topics like research planning, collaboration strategies, diverse scientific communication methods, science-media relations, and securing European grants. The course featured insightful discussions with prominent guests including Dr. Vernesa Smolčić, Dr. Ana Černok, Dušan Pavlović, Milica Ninković, and Ivan Umeljčić. This immersive experience enriched Minja's understanding of effective science communication in today's dynamic landscape.

Figure 23. MSc Minja Mladenović at "How to Communicate Modern Science?" course in Belgrade

3.8 Lecture on “Functional Magnetic Resonance Imaging (fMRI) and Future Perspectives for Mapping Neurological Activity”

Staff involved: MSc Mirjana Mundžić

Place: Faculty of Biology, University of Belgrade

Date: 08 April 2024

Website: N/A

Goal: Introduction to Functional Magnetic Resonance Imaging (fMRI) and Future Perspectives for Mapping Neurological Activity

Brief report:

The lecture on “Functional Magnetic Resonance Imaging (fMRI) and Future Perspectives for Mapping Neurological Activity” was given by dr Goran Angelovski, Senior Researcher from the Laboratory of Molecular and Cellular Neuroimaging at the International Center for Primate Brain Research, Center for Excellence in Brain Sciences and Intelligence Technologies (CEBSIT), Chinese Academy of Sciences in Shanghai, China.

Dr Angelovski's expertise lies in the field of neuroscience, with a focus on advanced brain imaging techniques and their applications. During the lecture, he provided insights into the latest developments in functional magnetic resonance imaging and its role in understanding neurological activity. He discussed recent research findings and methodologies employed by the Center for Excellence in Brain Sciences and Intelligence

Technologies, Shanghai. The presentation highlighted the importance of international collaboration in advancing brain research which facilitates the exchange of knowledge and expertise, fostering innovation and progress in neuroscience and related fields.

Figure 24. MSc Mirjana Mundžić at lecture on “Functional Magnetic Resonance Imaging (fMRI) and Future Perspectives for Mapping Neurological Activity” given by dr Goran Angelovski